

FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND THEIR PRACTICAL IMPORTANCE

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu ilmiy maqola ilmiy xarakterga ega bo'lib, uning amaliy ahamiyati mavzu va mavzuga oid misol va masalalarni tahlil hamda tadqiqi hisoblanadi. Ilmiy maqolada kasr-tartibli differensial tenglamalar haqida so'z yuritiladi hamda bir qator natijalarga erishilgan. Fizika va boshqa tabiiy fanlar masalalari differensial tenglamalar nazariyasini muammolar bilan ta'minlab turadi. Ammo shunday ham bo'lish mumkinki, matematik tadqiqotlar, bir oz vaqt o'tganidan so'ng aniq fizikaviy muammolarda o'z aksini topadi.

Annotation: This scientific article has a scientific character, and its practical significance is the analysis and research of examples and issues related to the topic. The scientific article talks about fractional differential equations and a number of results have been achieved. Problems of physics and other natural sciences provide the theory of differential equations with problems. But it is also possible that mathematical research, after some time has passed, finds its reflection in concrete physical problems.

Kalit so'zlar: Kasr-tartibli differensial tenglama, Laplas almashtirish, ketma-ketlik, Volterra, ikkinchi tur integral, operator, obraz, umumiy yechim, erkli o'zgaruvchi.

Key words: Fractional differential equation, Laplace substitution, sequence, Volterra, integral of the second kind, operator, image, general solution, arbitrary variable.

Agar tenglamada y erkli o'zgaruvchi, $y(x)$ noma'lum funksiya va uning kasr tartibli hosilalari qatnashsa, bunday tenglamalar *kasr tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamalar* deyiladi. Oddiy differensial tenglamalar nazariyasiga o'xshash kasr tartibli oddiy differensial tenglamalar ham chiziqli, bir jinsli va bir jinsli bo'lmagan o'zgaruvchi koeffitsientli va o'zgaruvchi koeffitsientli turlarga bo'linadi. Bizga malumki kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalarni *ketma-ket* yaqinlashish usuli bilan xam *Laplas almashtirishi* dan foydalanib xam yechish mumkin, biz ikkala usulni xam bayon qilishga xarakat qilamiz.

Masala. Quyidagi

$$D_{ax}^{\alpha} y(x) - \lambda y(x) = f(x) \quad (a < x \leq b; \alpha > 0; n = [\alpha] + 1; \lambda \in R) \quad (2.3.1)$$

kasr tartibli chiziqli differensial tenglamani ketma – ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan va Laplas almashtirishidan foydalanib umumiy yechimini toping.

(2.3.1) tenglamani quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozib olamiz:

$$D_{ax}^{\alpha}y(x) = \lambda y(x) + f(x).$$

Hosil bo‘lgan tenglikning har ikki tomoniga $D_{ax}^{-\alpha}$ teskari operatorni qo‘llaymiz:

$$D_{ax}^{-\alpha}D_{ax}^{\alpha}y(x) = D_{ax}^{-\alpha}(\lambda y(x) + f(x)).$$

U holda (1.2.20) va (1.2.8) formulalarga asosan

$$y(x) - \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{[D_{ax}^{\alpha-j-1}y(x)]_{x=a}}{\Gamma(\alpha-j)}(x-a)^{\alpha-j-1} = \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}}$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bu tenglikda j ni $j-1$ bilan almashtirib,

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{[D_{ax}^{\alpha-j}y(x)]_{x=a}}{\Gamma(\alpha-j+1)}(x-a)^{\alpha-j} + \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}}$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

Bu tenglamada quyidagicha belgilash kiritib olamiz

$$C_j = [D_{ax}^{\alpha-j}y(x)]_{x=a}$$

natijada tenglama quyidagicha ko‘rinishga keladi:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha-j+1)}(x-a)^{\alpha-j} + \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}}$$

(2.3.2)

Bu (2.3.2) tenglama Volterraning ikkinchi tur integral tenglamasi ekanligini anglash qiyin yemas. Bizga integral tenglamalar kursidan malumki bunday integral tenglamalar odatda ketma - ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan yechiladi. Biz ham (2.3.2) integral tenglamani yechish uchun ketma-ket yaqinlashish usulini qo‘llaymiz.

U holda quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$y_0(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha-j+1)}(x-a)^{\alpha-j}, \quad (2.3.3)$$

$$y_m(x) = y_0(x) + \frac{\lambda}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{y_{m-1}(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x \frac{f(t)dt}{(x-t)^{1-\alpha}} \quad (m \in N). \quad (2.3.4)$$

Agar (1.2.8) va (2.3.3) larni e‘tiborga olsak, $y_1(x)$ uchun quyidagi

$$\begin{aligned} y_1(x) &= y_0(x) + \lambda D_{ax}^{-\alpha}y_0(x) + D_{ax}^{-\alpha}f(x) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha-j+1)}(x-a)^{\alpha-j} + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha-j+1)} D_{ax}^{-\alpha}(x-a)^{\alpha-j} + D_{ax}^{-\alpha}f(x) = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(2\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{2\alpha - j} + D_{ax}^{-\alpha} f(x)$$

ifodani topamiz. Natijada

$$y_1(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{i-1} (x - a)^{\alpha i - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha i - j + 1)} + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} f(t) dt \quad (2.3.5)$$

ni hosil qilamiz.

Shunga o‘xshash (2.3.3) va (2.3.5) larni qo‘llab:

$$\begin{aligned} y_2(x) &= y_0(x) + \lambda D_{ax}^{-\alpha} y_1(x) + D_{ax}^{-\alpha} f(x) = \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{C_j}{\Gamma(\alpha - j + 1)} (x - a)^{\alpha - j} + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{i-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha i - j + 1)} D_{ax}^{-\alpha} (x - a)^{\alpha i - j} + \\ &+ D_{ax}^{-\alpha} f(x) + D_{ax}^{-\alpha} D_{ax}^{-\alpha} f(x) \end{aligned}$$

ni hosil qilamiz. (1.2.20) va (1.2.8) formulalarga asosan

$$y_2(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\lambda^{i-1} (x - a)^{\alpha i - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha i - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\lambda^{i-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha i)} (x - t)^{\alpha i - 1} \right] f(t) dt \quad (2.3.6)$$

ifodani olamiz.

Bu jarayonni davom ettirib, $y_m(x)$ uchun quyidagi formulani olamiz:

$$y_m(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=1}^{m+1} \frac{\lambda^{i-1} (x - a)^{\alpha i - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha i - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{i=1}^m \frac{\lambda^{i-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha i)} (x - t)^{\alpha i - 1} \right] f(t) dt. \quad (2.3.7)$$

Bu tenglikda $m \rightarrow \infty$ da limitga o‘tib, (2.3.2) 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamasining yechimini oshkor ko‘rinishda topamiz:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{i-1} (x - a)^{\alpha i - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha i - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^{i-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha i)} (x - t)^{\alpha i - 1} \right] f(t) dt,$$

yoki i indeksni $i - 1$ bilan almashtirsak,

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^i (x - a)^{\alpha i + \alpha - j}}{\Gamma(\alpha i + \alpha - j + 1)} + \int_a^x \left[\sum_{i=0}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda^i}{\Gamma(\alpha i + \alpha)} (x - t)^{\alpha i + \alpha - 1} \right] f(t) dt. \quad (2.3.8)$$

Agar (1.1.22) ni inobatga olsak, bu (2.3.8) yechimni quyidagi ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin:

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) &= \sum_{j=1}^n C_j (x - a)^{\alpha - j} E_{\alpha, \alpha - j + 1} \left[\lambda (x - a)^{\alpha} \right] + \\ &+ \int_a^x (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} E_{\alpha, \alpha} \left[\lambda (x - t)^{\alpha} \right] f(t) dt. \quad (2.3.9) \end{aligned}$$

Demak (2.3.1) tenglama (2.3.9) ko‘rinishdagi umumiy yechimga ega.

Endi (2.3.1) tenglamani Laplas almashtirishidan foydalanib yechamiz. Ma'lumki, (2.3.1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimini topish uchun avval unga mos bir jinsli differensial tenglamaning yechimi topiladi, chunki u bizga umumiy yechimni topishda kerak bo'ladi. (2.3.1) tenglamaga mos bir jinsli differensial tenglama quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega:

$$D_{ax}^{\alpha}y(x) - \lambda y(x) = 0. \quad (2.3.10)$$

(2.3.1) tenglamadagi a ni nolga teng bo'lsin deb faraz qilaylik. Unda (2.3.10) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha}y(x) - \lambda y(x) = 0. \quad (2.3.11)$$

Endi (2.3.11) ning har - bir hadiga Laplas almashtirishini qo'llaymiz. Qulaylik uchun $y(x)$ ning Laplas operatoridagi obrazini $y(s)$ deb belgilasak va (1.3.20) hamda (1.3.21) larni inobatga olsak :

$$L[D_{0x}^{\alpha}y(x)] = s^{\alpha}y(s) - \sum_{j=1}^n C_j s^{j-1}, \quad L[\lambda y(x)] = \lambda y(s)$$

tengliklarga ega bo'lamiz. Bu tengliklarni (2.3.11) ga qo'yamiz va soddalashtiramiz:

$$s^{\alpha}y(s) - \sum_{j=1}^n C_j s^{j-1} - \lambda y(s) = 0,$$

$$y(s) = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n C_j s^{j-1}}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda} = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \frac{s^{j-1}}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda}.$$

Agar $\eta = \alpha, \xi = \alpha - j + 1, \rho = \lambda$ deb belgilash kiritsak va (1.3.23) ni inobatga olsak, $y(s)$ ning asli quyidagicha topiladi:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j x^{\alpha-j} E_{\alpha, \alpha-j+1}(\lambda x^{\alpha}) \quad (2.3.12)$$

Biz yuqorida $a = 0$ bo'lsin deb faraz qilgan edik, agar $a \neq 0$ bo'lsa, (2.3.12) funksiya quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j (x-a)^{\alpha-j} E_{\alpha, \alpha-j+1}(\lambda(x-a)^{\alpha}). \quad (2.3.13)$$

Endi (2.3.1) tenglamani bir jinsli bo'lmagan holda yechimini topamiz;

$$D_{ax}^{\alpha}y(x) - \lambda y(x) = f(x),$$

tenglama yechimini topamiz. Bu tenglikdagi a ni nolga teng bo'lsin deb faraz qilaylik. Unda u quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega bo'ladi:

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha}y(x) - \lambda y(x) = f(x) \quad (2.3.14)$$

Endi (2.3.14) tenglikni har – bir hadi uchun Laplas almashtirishini qo‘llaymiz va qulaylik uchun $y(x)$ ning obrazini $y(s)$ hamda $f(x)$ ning obrazini $f(s)$ deb belgilash kiritsak,

$$L[D_{0t}^{\alpha}y(x)] = s^{\alpha}y(s) - \sum_{j=1}^n C_j s^{j-1}, L[\lambda y(x)] = \lambda y(s), L[f(x)] = f(s),$$

tengliklarga ega bo‘lamiz. Bu tengliklarni (2.3.14) ga qo‘yib, so‘ngra soddalashtiramiz:

$$s^{\alpha}y(s) - \sum_{j=1}^n C_j s^{j-1} - \lambda y(s) = f(s),$$

$$y(s) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \frac{s^{j-1}}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda} + \frac{f(s)}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda}. \quad (2.3.15)$$

Yuqorida topilgan $y(s)$ ni $y(s) = y(s)_1 + y(s)_2$ ko‘rinishda yozish mumkin, bu yerda

$$y(s)_1 = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j \frac{s^{j-1}}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda}, y(s)_2 = \frac{f(s)}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda}. \quad (2.3.16)$$

$y(s)_1$ ni aslini biz yuqorida (2.3.13) ko‘rinishida topgan edik . Biz endi $y(s)_2$ ning aslini topamiz. Bizga ma’lumki $y(s)_2$ ning asli Grin funksiyasidan foydalanib quyidagicha topiladi:

$$y(x)_2 = \int_0^x G_{\alpha,\beta}(x-t)f(t)dt .$$

Bu yerda $G_{\alpha,\beta}(x)$ - (2.3.1) tenglamaning Grin funksiyasi bo‘lib Laplas operatori orqali quyidagicha topiladi:

$$G_{\alpha,\beta}(x) = \left(L^{-1} \left[\frac{1}{s^{\alpha} - \lambda} \right] \right).$$

Agar $\eta = \alpha, \xi = \alpha, \rho = \lambda$ deb belgilash kiritsak va (1.3.23) ni inobatga olsak, $G_{\alpha,\beta}(x)$ ni quyidagicha ko‘rinishda topamiz:

$$G_{\alpha,\alpha}(x) = x^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(\lambda x^{\alpha}),$$

Natijada $y(x)_2$ ni quyidagicha ko‘rinishiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$y(x)_2 = \int_0^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(\lambda(x-t)^{\alpha})f(t)dt. \quad (2.3.17)$$

Biz yuqorida $a = 0$ bo‘lsin deb faraz qilgan edik , agar $a \neq 0$ bo‘lsa, (2.3.17) funksiya quyidagicha ko‘rinishga ega bo‘ladi:

$$y(x)_2 = \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha,\alpha}(\lambda(x-t)^{\alpha})f(t)dt. \quad (2.3.18)$$

Biz yuqoridagi (2.3.13), (2.3.15), (2.3.16), (2.3.18) tengliklarni inobatga olsak (2.3.1) tenglamaning umumiy yechimi quyidagicha ko‘rinishda ekanligi kelib chiqadi:

$$y(x) = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j (x-a)^{\alpha-j} E_{\alpha, \alpha-j+1} \left[\lambda (x-a)^\alpha \right] + \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} E_{\alpha, \alpha} \left[\lambda (x-t)^\alpha \right] f(t) dt .$$

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